

The Degree Of Availability Of The Dimensions Of The Learning Organization With The School Administration In Secondary Schools In Hawalli Educational District - Girls And Obstacles To Their Application

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 10,2023</p> <p>Accepted: December 12,2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Asymmetrical Structure, Code-Switching, Content Morphemes, System Morphemes, Matrix Language Frame Model, Urdu-English Codeswitching</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10349942</p>	<p><i>This study aimed to identify the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization among school administrations in secondary schools in the Hawalli Educational Area - Girls and obstacles to their application, and to detect differences in the views of the respondents due to the job experience and job title or degree. The study population included all teachers and heads of scientific departments as well as principals and assistant principals in secondary schools in Hawalli Educational Zone (girls). The study followed the descriptive analytical approach using a two-part questionnaire including demographic data and 7 dimensions, which included 46 items, and was applied to (267) teachers and (25) department heads. A structured interview tool was also used and applied to two principals and four assistant principals in two schools in the study population. The quantitative results indicated the availability of the dimensions of the learning organization in these schools in varying degrees from high to medium, while the qualitative results indicated that there is an application of some dimensions of the organization, but not at the required level. Further, there are some obstacles to the application of these dimensions, such as material obstacles and the lack of awareness of these schools of the concept of the learning organization. The results also indicated that there are statistically significant differences due to the academic qualification in favour of the postgraduate graduates, and there are also statistically significant differences for some dimensions of the organization due to the job level in favour of the managers</i></p>

Introduction

The past century has been a time of rapid change and transformation in various fields, which imposed a need to adopt contemporary approaches to keep pace. So, globalization, technology, and knowledge economies have become fundamental to work systems, and quality and institutional excellence have become more critical for organizations, including education institutions.

The adoption of organizational change based on collective performance, continuous education, and the pursuit of constant improvement has become essential to ensure institutional competitiveness.

The learning organization as a modern administrative concept contributes to advancing educational institutions' ability to bring about required change at the individual, collective, and institutional levels. Thus, the learning organization and its executive dimensions are based on administrative flexibility and the transfer of knowledge between employees, which can transform into new practices that improve the performance of the institution according to a common vision and goals.

Study problem

General education schools have many problems that reduce the quality of the educational process and weaken its outputs. However, with modern administrative concepts, such as the learning organization, a qualitative leap in school performance can be achieved. These institutions may improve their performance by providing continuous learning opportunities for their affiliates and encouraging them to work cooperatively and adopt a collective vision guided by strategic leadership. Hence, the problem of the study lies in identifying school performance in public education, especially secondary education, and the extent to which its departments practice modern administrative concepts. Despite the importance of this concept and the call for educators to adopt it, there are many obstacles in the application, such as adherence to old administrative concepts and resistance to change. The problem of the research is determined by identifying the most important obstacles to the application of the learning organization, so as to help educators in reaching sound methodologies to apply modern administrative concepts more effectively.

Questions

1. What is the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization with the school administration in secondary schools—girls in Hawalli Educational Zone—from the point of view of teachers?
2. What is the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization with the school administration in secondary schools—girls in Hawalli Educational Zone—from the point of view of school administrators?
3. What are the most important obstacles to the implementation of the dimensions of the learning organization in secondary schools—girls in Hawalli Educational Zone—from the point of view of school administrators?
4. Are there statistically significant differences at the 0.05 level in the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization in secondary schools—girls in Hawalli Educational Zone—due to variation in academic qualification, job experience, and job title?

Importance

The importance in focusing on the learning organization as a contemporary administrative concept—whether applied in educational institutions, or the government or private sector—is that a theory that has the greatest ability to ensure growth, competition, learning and development. Further, it can respond to environmental changes and enable organizations to exchange participatory knowledge among its members to develop their performance in line with contemporary ideas. This helps the organization or institution to ensure continuous development.

Studies on the feasibility of institutional management from the perspective of the learning organization encourage educational institutions to adopt and apply the contemporary concept to ensure the quality of its outputs, which is a modernist concept.

This study is one of the few studies in the State of Kuwait that deals with the concept of the learning organization and measures the availability of its elements in a governmental educational institution. Most previous studies were in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, which reflect the interest in their own educational institutions.

This study derives its theoretical importance by introducing the effectiveness of applying the basic dimensions of the learning system, such as continuous learning, effective dialogue, knowledge sharing and a positive impact on teachers, school administration or the institution in general. Also, this study will identify the obstacles facing government educational institutions when they adopt the dimensions of the learning organization to avoid and overcome them.

Goals

1. Identifying the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization with the school administration in secondary schools in the Hawalli Educational Zone for girls.
2. Identifying the most important obstacles to the application of the dimensions of the learning organization in secondary schools in the Hawalli Educational Zone for girls from the point of view of the sample.
3. Detecting statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization in secondary schools in the Hawalli Educational Zone for girls due to the variable of academic qualification, job experience, and job title.

Limitations of the study

- **Time limits:** This study was applied in the second semester of academic year 2022-2023.
- **Spatial boundaries:** This study was conducted in secondary schools in the Hawalli Educational Zone for girls.
- **Objective limits:** This study is limited to knowing the dimensions applied to the concept of the learning organization in secondary schools in the Hawalli Educational Zone for girls: creating opportunities for continuous learning, encouraging interrogation and dialogue, encouraging cooperation and collective learning, empowering workers to bring them toward a common vision, establishing systems for sharing knowledge and learning, linking the organization to the external environment, and strategic leadership. This study will also focus on identifying the most important obstacles that hinder the application of some dimensions of the concept of the learning organization in general education schools.
- **Human Limits:** This study was applied to the educational and administrative staff in secondary schools in the Hawalli Educational Zone for girls (heads of departments and teachers and senior management represented by principals and assistant directors) in two out of ten schools in the Hawalli Educational Zone.

Study terminology and procedural definitions

Learning Organization: "A continuous process from the vision of the members of the organization, as this process aims to invest the expertise and experiences of the organization and monitor the information resulting from these experiences and experiences in the memory of the organization or institution and then review them from time to time to benefit from them in solving the problems it faces, whether as an organization or its affiliated individuals, within the framework of support and assistance from the leadership of the organization in particular and organizational culture in general" (Al-Maghrabi&Marzouk, 2016, p. 14 of Hegan, 1998). Also procedurally defined by Senge 1990, as "an organization that continuously expands its ability to create truly desirable outcomes, provides room for collective ambition, enables people to learn how to learn from each other, and nurtures new and extended modes of thinking" (p.18).

Theoretical framework and previous studies

First: Theoretical Framework

The idea of the learning organization was initiated in the early '70s by educators such as Shine (1985), Schien (1990), Garrin (1993), and Keezer (2005) who suggested that learning organization emerged because Americans were "unable to face the challenges of the external environment in their organizations under the rule of inflexible bureaucratic cultures and routine work that limits creative thinking; so came an educated organization that is adaptable, flexible, experiment-based and renewable" (Al-Fakhri & Al-Moayyad, 2022, p. 733).

Many specialists believe that the learning organization is attributed to Argyris and Schon. In the '60s, Argyris focused his research on the impact of organizational structures, personnel management and the way employees adapt to their organizations. In 1970, he studied the incompatibility between individual needs and organizational requirements, which often leads to frustration, failure, and lack of adaptation. At the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, he met Schön, whose work focused on the implications of training and learning on individuals' practices, and that change that is a key element in the development of learning and adaptable social systems. Argyris and Schon defined an educational organization as "the process of detecting and correcting errors," and in order for an organization to become more efficient, it must learn from its mistakes, this is how he developed his theory of learning in circles" (Laraj&Nasreddin, 2023, p. 226).

Since Peter Singh launched the term "learning organization" in 1990, this concept has expanded. "The works of (Revas, 1983) and the writings of (Senge, 1990) are the real beginning of the emergence of the term learning organization in an integrated manner" (Al-Ruwaili, 2022, p. 129).

The learning organization is the product of administrative concepts and theories from management science and its theories. It began with the traditional school of management, followed by the behavioural school or the so-called human relations, and the quantitative introduction to the science of managing institutions and individuals. This led to the establishment of the systems school and the situational school in 1960. After 30 years of industrial change and technological development, administrative and human studies characterized by renewal, modernity, and flexibility, in both their philosophy and dimensions, including the learning organization, have emerged.

Kafi (2018) developed a model for the development of administrative schools derived from Najm (2005) through which he illustrated the chronology and development in management science and theories (appendix 1).

The concept of a learning organization

The learning organization is interested in science and knowledge and raises the slogan of "management with knowledge" and seeks to apply this slogan with all its effort. The subject of learning organizations has received increasing attention, as it has become a vital topic in contemporary administrative thought.

The definitions of the learning organization vary according to researchers' philosophies and their expertise and experiences; most definitions mention that the learning organization revolves around the power of learning in transforming vision into reality. Odor (2018) defined the learning organization as the place where employees excel in developing, possessing, and transferring knowledge. This knowledge consists of three building blocks: A permanent environment for learning, obvious learning practices, and leadership behaviour that enhances learning.

A learning organization is "an organization that seeks to enhance its ability to create, acquire and develop knowledge continuously, reconsider its knowledge and ideas and benefit from the results of this in building its future through key elements" (Al-Duaj, 2019, p. 389). The key elements include personal commitment, the creation of a shared vision, team learning, and thinking systems.

In education, the learning organization is a "school that seeks to continuously develop its performance to adapt to organizational and social change by localizing learning in its internal culture, developing understanding and organized teamwork among its employees" (Al-Mabala'a, 2021, p. 121). The school wants to develop its abilities to the highest degree of performance.

It also defines the learning organization in the school field as "the ability of the school organization to develop itself continuously through the availability of dimensions of personal mastery, systems thinking, teamwork, common vision and mental models" (Al-Ajmi, 2022, p. 21).

Al Hammadi (2021, p. 172) defined a learning organization as "the educational institution whose members participate in the development and formulation of organizational strategic plans that make them able to apply continuous learning, self-development, exchange of information and experiences, acquire and produce knowledge, and keep pace with developments.

Ultimately, the learning organization is the one in which continuous learning processes are ensured, and capabilities are developed for all institution members and everyone who deals with the institution. There is focus on the continuous development of the institution as a whole, and work to develop channels between individuals' learning and the organization's policies and strategies.

The researchers define the learning school organization as "that school (organization) that responds dynamically to all changes and challenges that may occur, internal or external, through the localization of knowledge, learning, training and participation to provide all school members (student, teacher, school administration) with the necessary skills to meet the demands of the market and new situations in the educational fields.

Characteristics of the learning organization

Learning organizations are characterized by a number of features: the presence of social values, administrative empowerment, the power of communication and communication, leadership commitment, knowledge transfer and outstanding performance. The continuity of the learning process in the organization, the existence of a common vision among organization members, the dependence of learning on the experiences of the organization, the acquisition of information and its use in solving the organization's current and future problems are characteristics; further learning is an automatic and continuous process (Al-Meligy, 2010, p. 240). Al-Hawajrah and Sobh (2021, p. 98) and Al-Harthy (2013, p. 50) pointed to the availability of a strategic plan that looks to a better future for the institution through continuous awareness of the institution's reality and the adoption of a common future vision, which translate into clear and specific projects for the development of its affiliates. It should provide a safe work environment that encourages creativity, development, and innovation based on participatory cooperative work. One of the most important characteristics of the learning organization is that it benefits from previous experiences to be more flexible and transfer knowledge within the institution. The learning organization is characterized by the ability to formulate problem-solving strategies, speed up sound decision-making, and provide opportunities to participate in decision-making. The learning organization invests in human resources at various administrative levels with the maximum possible capacity. In a related context, Al-Thiab (2014) explained that the learning organization has a number of characteristics:

1. **The ability to adapt quickly to events:** The learning organization encourages learning, works to increase the cognitive abilities of its members and has wide knowledge of its members. This helps it to adapt positively to the events it faces.
2. **Targeting:** The process of becoming a learning organization is organized and planned, not random, and it expresses a positive interaction and has a clear direction and a known goal.
3. **Participation:** The organization needs positive interaction; this can only be done by providing a stimulating environment and an encouraging atmosphere for the organization to show and enhance the positive aspects and reduce the negative aspects.
4. **Empowerment:** It means giving individuals the necessary powers and authority to work and move freely, and the ability to encourage others to achieve goals.
5. **The ability to develop and innovate:** The learning organization is always working to encourage its employees to achieve more creativity, innovation, development, and progress, benefiting from the support for the learning and self-development processes of employees.

Through the presentation of the characteristics of the learning organization, it is clear that modern learning organizations have shifted from a routine-based administrative concept to a dynamic concept based on sustainable development and continuous learning to help achieve the professional development of its affiliates in the face of challenges and solving them in more creative ways. In adopting the learning organization, the educational institution moves from a limited closed environment to a more conducive open environment that is risk facing and adaptable, as it is an institution based on knowledge management, employment, and its ability to make enhance competition about learning, thus increasing constituents' abilities and skills.

The importance of transforming traditional educational organizations into learning organizations

Educational systems are constantly under multiple pressures, putting educational organizations in front of challenges that need to be faced through continuous learning. These organizations transform into learning organizations that do not provide education services only, that is, organizations in a state of learning, in which their affiliates (i.e., administrators, faculty members, staff, and students) learn continuously to avoid mistakes, and overcome difficulties.

The importance of the learning organization is also highlighted by the unique capabilities and advantages it provides that improve the performance and development of organizations. A number of basic points (Harb, 2018) are as follows:

1. Support creativity and improve and reform education.
2. Prepare the organization to accept change and invest knowledge.
3. Increase the organization's members' motivation and deal with changes in work methods.
4. Transfer the impact of training and assist the organization in handling rapid change.

It is clear that the importance of the learning organization (school) is to build the professional internal competence of the school, invest in the learning energies of each teacher and share them among school members, prepare the school to assume responsibility for professional development, make learning a permanent feature, spread the culture and experience of distinguished schools to other schools, and apply modern educational strategies in the school to ensure its survival and guide its practice in modern scientific guidance, and to enhance the survival of the school's professional excellence and build expertise and capabilities to overcome obstacles to professional development.

Goals of the learning organization

The learning organization seeks to enhance its ability to create, acquire, and develop knowledge, and benefit from the results in building the organization (Al-Duaij, 2019).

One of the most important objectives of the learning organization is its reliance on creativity, innovation, ideas, and continuous learning from all organizational and environmental conditions; it also develops plans, organizational frameworks, strategies, and mechanisms to increase its ability to adapt to changes, face challenges, and successfully achieve its goals (Mezher, 2019).

The learning organization aims to create, acquire, and transfer knowledge, and modify people's behaviours to reflect new knowledge and visions in the organization to transform new ideas into improved performance. People are constantly working to expand their capabilities to create the results they desire, and the learning organization seeks new and broad ambitions, and people constantly learn to see the whole together. The learning organization: facilitates the learning of all its members and continuously transforms itself through the full participation of employees in the process of collective change that is made collaboratively, collectively responsible and directed toward shared values or principles, as most perceptions of the learning organization work on the assumption that learning is valuable, continuous and more effective when shared, and that each experience is an opportunity for learning. (Nakpodia, 2009, p. 80)

It also enables the learning organization to develop its organizational identity, retain learning members, useful communications, marketing, identification of internal expertise, innovative and creative development, and managerial socio analysis (Anjaria, 2020).

It is clear the objective of the learning organization is to improve the ability to adapt to changes successfully, and to achieve a competitive advantage of the organization's human resources by developing the knowledge of the organization's employees and translating knowledge into new ways of work by combining the ability to manage knowledge and change for the better.

Requirements for building a learning organization

Learning organizations are the result of planning. Building a learning organization requires management and employees' exceptional efforts to adopt integrated and comprehensive thinking systems that are designed, developed, and sustained through vision, values, communication, policy selection, organizational structure, methods and procedures, and keeping pace with developments.

Kafi (2018, p. 289–290) identified requirements for building a learning organization:

1. **The organization's strategy** includes the educational approach, where the organization's strategy must be formulated from the perspective of knowledge, as knowledge-based organizations define their strategy based on their knowledge and the need to shift the strategy of organizations from competitive to cooperative, and make changes that represent the movement of organizations away from their current state to a desirable future state.
2. **Looking inside the organization:** Knowledge is one of the most important requirements for transforming into a learning organization. The organization must have the ability to acquire, disseminate, and distribute knowledge and benefit from its results by managing it, and by working to develop intellectual capital to improve organizational performance, accountability, and organizational control.
3. **Organization structure:** The structures used in learning organizations encourage a state of mastery, especially if the roles are visible, allowing the opportunity to align with the needs of internal customers and suppliers, as well as allowing for the personal development of employees, and the need to shift the structures of the organization from vertical to horizontal and shift tasks from routine to empowerment.

4. **Looking outside the organization:** Organizations rely on individuals who deal with external parties and prepare them as environmental survey systems, doing benchmarking and organizational environmental learning.
5. **Learning opportunities** are represented by the educational climate in that the organization has a climate that encourages individuals to learn and develop their potential. Self-development is where all employees are keen to develop themselves through seminars, meetings and other activities and are able to learn, innovate and pursue long-term visions.

In a related context, Al-Wahaid and Al-Fantoh (2020) indicated that the requirements for building the learning organization can be divided into three basic requirements:

1. **Administrative and organizational requirements:** These are administrative procedures that help implement the learning organization, characterized by trust, cooperation, critical thinking, encouraging questions, empowering teachers to participate in decision-making.
2. **Material and technical requirements:** They are the procedures related to the provision of financial and material requirements and technical equipment that contribute to knowledge sharing through a network of advanced computers that facilitate access to and storage of information, as well as the school building and facilities.
3. **Human requirements:** These are the procedures related to the provision of qualified and trained humans who contribute to achieving the concept of the learning organization; these requirements relate to the knowledge and skills possessed by teachers, human relations among them, and their training needs.

Leadership is a primary characteristic of the learning organization, which supports an inclusive learning culture in the organization; leadership for learning is a comprehensive construction and a key driver of work in the learning organization; leaders promote opportunities for continuous learning, dialogue, inquiry, empowerment and group learning (Zubr, 2019).

Accordingly, an important building requirement for the learning organization is distinguished and contemporary administrative leadership. Leadership does not stem from the prerogatives and instructions related to control, follow-up and evaluation only, leadership needs a high degree of interaction and participation, and if the educational administration wants to reach global levels, its leaders must be interactive leaders who participate with everyone in achieving their desired goals.

Dimensions of the learning organization

There are many of dimensions of the learning organization, which the educational organizations must adopt if they want to reach it. The most important of which are:

1. **Professional growth field:** Professional growth is the organized and continuous effort to improve the cognitive, administrative, and technical capabilities of individuals, bring about positive changes in their attitudes, and improve the culture of work (Kahwan, 2012). The skills necessary to meet the demands of modern society require upgrading the reality of the teacher and developing him professionally and socially. By providing training opportunities that give him professional competence, he keeps pace with new practices and raises his ability to understand the culture of students and develop moral qualities, values and behaviours that are commensurate with the teaching profession (Al-Ghamdi, 2013).
2. **The field of organizational structure:** It includes the design of the organization for environmental variables, which emphasizes participation rather than giving directions, in addition to the flexibility and speed of response and greater powers (Al-Diab, 2014).
3. **Experimentation:** Both Gibran (2011) and Abdel Fattah (2013) pointed out that experimentation includes the search for new knowledge using the scientific method, as the learning organization allows experimentation with and looks at mistakes as opportunities to learn from one's own experiences.
4. **Organizational climate:** Refers to features "that characterize the organization's environment that affect the behavioural frameworks of individuals, groups and organizations alike, according to which its impact determines the achievement of job satisfaction and motivation and its reflection on the organization's ability to achieve its goals efficiently and effectively" (Al-Rumaisa, 2014, p. 28).
5. **Systems thinking:** It is the ability of school staff to understand the intertwined relationships in the learning process within a set of school controls that contribute to the creation of measures in the educational process, which are based on making meaningful decisions.

Some of the researchers referred to in Abu Deeb (2022, p. 40–41) stated that the dimensions of the learning organization are as follows:

1. **Continuous learning:** We mean growth through learning and employing experiences and events. This can be achieved at the individual, team, and organizational level, which helps in achieving the goals so that all see development or improvement, as the process of continuous learning involves the principle

of continuous change in the way of thinking to realize new concepts and knowledge and then work with them.

2. **Encouraging dialogue:** Dialogue is a valuable social skill, and the institution applies the concept of the learning organization by spreading the culture of dialogue. When the organization moves away from open dialogue, it falls into bickering and conflict. Dialogue is linked to the prevailing culture in society and transparency encourages the spread of a culture of positive dialogue in any society.
3. **Personal Empowerment:** Personal empowerment can be reached by adopting a continuous learning approach, which makes individuals more able to achieve desired goals. Personal empowerment refers to the availability of personal ingenuity that enhances self-motivation to learn how our actions affect the environment, and to allow workers to increase their skills and knowledge and to provide creative solutions to the problems they face.
4. **Common vision:** It is the ability of employees to commit to the institutional vision, so that employees can look at the future of the organization with a similar vision, which leads to unifying their efforts in a joint work plan to reach the desired future and achieve goals.
5. **Collaboration and group learning:** This starts through dialogue and the ability of team members to enter into common thinking about things that cannot be achieved individually; the team must feel very confident to continue effective learning and knowledge sharing.

A group of researchers developed a model for the learning organization, and Marsik and Watkins (1996) developed a tool to measure the availability of its dimensions, which was called Dimensions of the Learning Organization Questionnaire (DLOQ).

In measuring the dimensions of the learning organization, the researchers adopted this model in designing the questionnaire to measure the presence of these dimensions in the administrative performance of the secondary schools in the Hawalli Educational Girls Educational Area. Which are as follows (a) the first dimension: creating opportunities for continuous learning, (b) the second dimension: encouraging questioning and dialogue, the third dimension: encouraging collaboration and group learning, the fourth dimension: creating systems for knowledge sharing and learning, the fifth dimension: empowering workers to bring them together toward a common vision, the sixth dimension: linking the organization to the external environment and the seventh dimension: strategic leadership.

Learning Organization Models

Today, organizations of all kinds have sought to build, develop, and synthesize knowledge to respond to rapid environmental changes such as globalization, informatics, technical development, and others. Accordingly, new ideas and visions have changed the nature of the work of organizations; therefore models have emerged for the learning organization.

The most important of these models include:

1. Peter Senge Model:

Senge (1990) presented a model for a learning organization on five elements:

- **Systems thinking:** It is an approach and framework based on seeing the whole instead of parts and seeing the interrelationships that bind the parts of the system.
- **Self-distinction:** It is constantly working to clarify and define the personal vision accurately and clearly, and to see reality objectively.
- **Mental models:** These assumptions, generalizations, and mental images are firmly established, which affect people's perception of the world and their interpretation of events around them.
- **A shared vision:** The ability of a group to paint a shared picture of a desired future.
- **Group learning:** The process by which the group efforts are organized, arranged, and unified to achieve results, and these foundations should be adhered to by the organization that seeks to be a learning organization (Al-Mabala'a, 2021).

2. Marsik & Watkins model:

Marsik and Watkins (1993) presented a model for the learning organization and identified two elements that overlap in influencing the organization's ability to change, namely individuals and organizational structure, and focused on continuous learning for all levels of learning. This includes all the sub-elements that overlap; the school is the basic building block in the social structure—social processes depend on it, and ambitions are built on it—because it builds generations that carry the aspirations of the nation. The learning process in schools includes input from students, teachers and administrators, and learning takes place at the individual and collective level. Thus, organizational learning has two types: individual learning for workers and group learning (Al-Zyood, 2021).

3. Markhardt's model of the learning organization (Marquardt, 1997)

This model consists of five subsystems that participate in achieving organizational learning and build the learning organization. These systems work interceptively, while the learning system is the

intersecting and overlapping system with the other subsystems and works to transform the organization into a learning organization. These dimensions are as follows:

Learning: Learning occupies an important place at all levels, and the learning system includes three levels: individual, group and organization.

Organizing: Organizing consists of four basic elements that have a clear impact on the behaviour of individuals: vision, culture, strategy and organizational structure.

Individuals: Individuals are one of the most important subsystems of the learning organization as its means and goal are achieved through the learning process.

Knowledge: This system is responsible for knowledge management in the organization and includes knowledge generation, acquisition and storage, data analysis, transfer, dissemination, and application (Marquardt, 2002).

4. Redding Model of the Learning Organization (Redding, 1997)

In this model, Redding proposed evaluating the learning organization based on the evaluation of companies, establishments, and organizations carried out by the centre for Strategic Learning in Naperville, Illinois, USA, which used various measurement tools. The model suggests that a specific scale should be chosen for the evaluation. The model includes six steps: Goal and Benefit Setting; Evaluation Tool Selection; Evaluation Management and Results Discovery; Developing the Strategy of the Learning Organization; Planning the Initiatives of the Learning Organization; Implementing the Learning Organization's Initiatives (Al-Rashoodi, 2007).

Second: Previous Studies

Many studies have dealt with the learning organization. Al-Shaya and Al-Sheikh (2022) aimed to identify the degree to which school administration practices the strategies of the learning organization in secondary schools for girls in Al-Ahsa according to the DLOQ model of the dimensions. The study found a high degree of school management of the strategies of the learning organization, and there were no statistically significant differences in the degree school administration practiced the strategies of the learning organization regardless of the nature of work and years of service, except for the field of strategic leadership supporting learning, where there were differences in favour of teachers.

Khanfar's study (2021) aimed to reveal the perceptions of public education teachers in the Eastern Province of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia toward their schools as learning organizations. The teachers' perceptions toward their schools as learning organizations obtained average approval scores: in descending order of approval: the field of professional growth, climate, experimentation, and then organizational structure. The results also showed the presence of statistically significant differences in the responses attributed to variation in academic qualification in all fields except the field of experimentation in favour of the lower qualification each time.

Al-Hammadi's study (2021) also aimed to identify the extent to which the dimensions of the learning organization are applied in government secondary schools for girls in Riyadh and to identify the obstacles to their application. After empowering employees to achieve a common vision followed by linking the organization to the external environment followed by the strategic leadership dimension, the results showed that the most important obstacles to the application of the dimensions of the learning organization in secondary schools are: the lack of training courses provided to school members, routine performance evaluation programs, and scarcity of cooperation with external supporters to develop advanced educational programs.

Al-Azmi's study (2021) aimed to develop a future vision for transforming middle schools in the State of Kuwait into learning organizations. The study used a questionnaire that was applied to a stratified random sample of 420 teachers from middle schools. All dimensions of the learning organization were of medium response, in order: intellectual models, then personal individual abilities and potentials, then group learning, then organized thinking. Finally, the results showed that there are statistically significant differences between the responses of the sample members according to gender, the years of experience, and the educational region.

Beljahr's study (2021) aimed to identify the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization in Wadi Hadhramaut secondary schools from the view of principals and teachers. The degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization was medium, and there were no statistically significant differences due to gender or number of years of experience. There were differences due to the nature of work in favour of managers.

Likewise, Al-Badawi and Al-Omari (2018) aimed to know the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization in government secondary schools in the United Arab Emirates. The study used a questionnaire with 180 principals of government secondary schools. The results of the study showed the availability of the dimensions of the organization are high, and there were no statistically significant differences due to gender, except for in encouraging dialogue, where the differences were statistically significant and in favour of women. In addition, there were no statistically significant differences due to

experience, except for the organizational field, where the differences were statistically significant for those with more than 10 years of experience.

Tan and Olaore (2021) aimed to identify the impact and effectiveness of the learning organization on the production of employees and management performance in the Republic of Turkey, and the study relied on the descriptive analytical approach. The study found a positive relationship between the effectiveness of the learning organization and the productivity of employees and administrative performance of the organization, which indicates that the impact of the learning organization is inclusive because it affects the effectiveness and efficiency of employees at every level.

Kools and Stoll (2016) aimed to develop a model for the school as a learning organization through an analytical literature review with the aim of developing an integrated model for the school as a learning organization in contemporary school organizations. The study established an integrated model for the school as a learning organization that focuses collectively on developing a shared vision of learning for all students, creating and supporting continuous learning opportunities for staff to promote group learning and collaboration, encouraging a culture of inquiry, innovation and exploration, and embedding systems for collecting and sharing knowledge with and from the external environment and the broader learning system, and modelling leadership learning.

Erdem and Okar (2013) also aimed to identify perceptions related to the learning organization in primary education. The descriptive survey approach based on the scales of perceptions related to the learning organization and organizational commitment was applied to 429 teachers from primary schools in the Turkish province of Van. The study identified a significant correlation between the dimensions of organizational commitment and the dimensions of the learning organization.

Hamzah et al. (2012) drew a random sample consisting of teachers with high levels of diversity in their previous academic backgrounds, majors of study, and years of teaching experience from schools located in Kuala Lumpur, and the state of Selangor, Malaysia. The data were collected through two standardized questionnaires from a psychometric perspective: Johnston & Caldwell Leadership Practices Questionnaire (LPQ) (2001) and Marquardt Learning Organization Questionnaire (LOQ) (2002). The results revealed a statistically significant correlation between leadership practices and the organization learning. The results revealed that the success of teachers' efforts and initiatives in transforming their schools into learning organizations is closely related to five main leadership practices: focus on improving students' academic achievement levels; continuous development of teaching, learning, and effective curricula; building cooperation, partnership within and outside the school system; building a stimulating and supportive school climate to advance reform; and the sustainable lifelong development of the school system.

Coldwell and Fried (2012) aimed to reveal the extent to which British schools can transform the learning organization system. The study adopted the Peter Singh model to compare the perceptions of human resources planners in Britain, Germany, and South Africa. The researchers interviewed 9 people specializing in human resources planning and found the culture and structure of the educational system affects the transformation toward the learning organization, especially in Europe, which adopts decentralization. So, the Singh model can succeed if cadres are trained and made aware of the learning organization. Yet, in South Africa, the system is still centralized and needs to be restructured to be able to become an educated organization to applying the Singh model.

Study procedure:

- Study Methodology

A descriptive-analytical approach was used, which aims to describe the phenomena of objects or events, collect facts and observations about them, and describe and analyse their conditions. In this study, a questionnaire was given to teachers and heads of departments, and semi-structured interviews with principals and assistant principals in secondary schools were conducted.

- Population and sample study

The study population consisted of all teachers, heads of scientific departments, principals, and assistant directors in the secondary schools for girls in Hawalli educational area (10 schools). The study was limited to two schools with their full educational and administrative bodies to achieve 2% of the total girls' schools in the secondary stage in Hawalli educational area, which included 267 teachers, 25 department heads, 2 directors, and 6 assistant directors.

Table (1) frequencies and percentages for demographic data		
	R	%

Job title	Head of department	21	12.1
	Teacher	153	87.9
Job experience	Less than 5 years	42	24.1
	5-10 years	37	21.3
	More than 10 years	95	54.6
Scientific qualifications	Bachelor's degree	160	92.0
	Postgraduate degree	14	8.0

Table 1 shows the variables according to job title, experience, and scientific qualifications, which is representative of the study sample. These data indicate the most general ratio is the category of teachers, then department heads, and the experiences vary and are representative of the spectra of the sample in both job experience and scientific qualifications. A high percentage of job experience of more than 10 years and having a bachelor's degree indicates the consistency of the sample.

Study Tools

After referring to the theoretical frameworks and previous Arab and foreign studies, the researchers designed an integrated questionnaire according to a model developed by Marsk and Watkins (1996) with seven dimensions of the learning organization (DLOQ).

The tool was designed with items in line with the educational institution in the State of Kuwait, the applied educational system, and the desired sample to achieve the objectives of the study (appendix 2). The questionnaire consisted of two parts: personal data (variables in the study, such as the variable of scientific level, years of experience, and job title). The second part consists of 7 dimensions with 46 items. The questionnaire was reviewed by four arbitrators specializing in the field of educational management and leadership. The interview tool for the sample of female and assistant directors was designed to add greater insight to the research questions.

Tool honesty

Virtual honesty, or what is known as the honesty of the arbitrators was used. The study tool was distributed to specialists in the field of educational management and leadership from the College of Basic Education and the College of Education, Kuwait University. Four arbitrators were used in addition to a review by the Department of Research and Studies in the Hawalli Educational Area of the Ministry of Education to ensure the study's sincerity and conformity with the sample and the environment in public education. The questionnaire was revised based on agreed upon observations by the arbitrators. The interview questions modified and approved before being applied to the sample, and ratified by the Research and Studies Department (appendix 3).

Tool stability

Table 1 (appendix 4) shows that the study tool is fixed in relation to its dimensions and gives the same results when reapplied. The tool achieved a level of stability on the correlation coefficients in high, acceptable, and consistent proportions in its internal dimensions. The total degree of the resolution is appropriate with what it intended to measure, which confirms the study tool is fixed with a correlation coefficient ranging between (.809-.965) and a stability rate of (0.91), which is an acceptable and statistically significant stability coefficient; the dimensions of the study were consistent with its items and its total dimensions and confirms its effectiveness in measuring the availability of the dimensions of the learning organization with school administration in the secondary schools of Hawalli Educational Area for girls and obstacles to its application.

Statistical processing:

The researchers used the statistical package program in the social sciences (SPSS) to analyse the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization in secondary schools and to detect statistically significant differences ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) in the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization in these schools due to variation in experience and job title. The following statistical methods were used: (a)

Cronbach alpha coefficient in order to extract the stability of the instrument, arithmetic averages and standard deviations, test for two independent samples T – TEST.

The results of the study:

The first study question: What is the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization with the school administration in secondary schools—girls in Hawalli educational area—from the point of view of teachers?

Data were collected from the questionnaire to answer this question. The dimensional tables were analysed separately and then the table of averages and total deviations of the dimensions of the learning organization was analysed.

The first dimension: creating opportunities for continuous learning

Table 2(appendix 4) shows results of the first study, where item 2 (cooperation of teachers in carrying out learning processes) ranked highest with an average of (4.70) and a standard deviation of (0.529), followed by item 3 (I discuss with teachers about functional errors in order to learn and benefit) with an average of (4.56) and a standard deviation of (0.574). The least common response were items 5 and 7, respectively. The sixth ranking included the confirmation of the study sample (management gives them enough time to learn during the school day) while it is (exchange of scientific experiences) with an average of (3.97) and a standard deviation of (0.879), and (obtaining rewards from management when learning new knowledge or skills) was last with an average of (3.89) and a standard deviation of (0.866).

The second dimension: encouraging interrogative and dialogue

Table 3(appendix 4) shows the arithmetic averages and standard deviations after the second study, where item 10 (management encourages me to ask and accept different questions) came in first with an average of (4.24) and a standard deviation of (0.719), followed by item 8 (teachers exchanging feedback with each other transparently) with an average of (4.23) and a standard deviation of (0.640). In last place, item 9 stated that (management listens to the views of others and is respected and appreciated) with an average of (3.71) and a standard deviation of (1.008).

The third dimension: encouraging collaboration and group learning

Table 4(appendix 4) shows item 12 came first (the school administration is keen on work based on the formation of teams in all fields) with an average of (4.08) and standard deviation of (0.741). Second, item 14 shows (the school administration deals with the members of the work teams equally regardless of any differences between them; average of (4.07) and standard deviation of (0.919)). Finally, item 13 (granting the school administration sufficient powers to the work teams to achieve the school's goals) had (3.84) average and standard deviation of (0.948).

The fourth dimension: creating systems for knowledge sharing and learning

Table 5(appendix 4) shows that after the fourth study, item 26 came in first (the school administration has measurement systems to know the results of training and development processes in the school and its impact on teachers) with an average of (4.05) and a standard deviation of (0.859), followed by item 25, which shows that (school administration allows everyone to benefit from its previous experiences) with an average of (4.04) and a standard deviation of (0.828). Item 22 (the school administration maintains up-to-date data on the skills possessed by female teachers) ranked last for this dimension with an average of (3.98) and a standard deviation of (0.886).

The fifth dimension: empowering workers to bring them together toward a common vision

Table 6(appendix 4) shows the fifth dimension of the study, in which item 28 ranked first (the school administration invites teachers to contribute and participate in enriching its strategic vision) with an average of (4.05) and a standard deviation of (0.848). Then, item 27 shows that (school administration allows freedom of choice for teachers when carrying out tasks) with an average of (4.02) and a standard deviation of (0.860). In last place, item 31 shows that (school administration supports everyone when carrying out their tasks, regardless of the risk) with an average of (3.94) and a standard deviation of (0.938).

The sixth dimension: linking the organization to the external environment

Table 7(appendix 4) shows the sixth dimension, from the first and second rank, respectively, for item 33 (the school administration encourages everyone to take into account the views of the beneficiaries [students and their parents] when making important decisions) with an average of (3.93) and a standard deviation of (1.012). item 32 (the school administration encourages everyone to think from a global perspective) with an average of (3.91) and a standard deviation of (0.975). Item 34 (the school administration is interested in knowing the impact of its decisions on the conditions of teachers) ranked last with an average of (3.81) and a standard deviation of (1.011).

The seventh dimension: Strategic Leadership

Table No. 8(appendix 4)for the seventh dimension shows that item 46 is first (managers transfer administrative expertise to teachers to empower them administratively and leadership) with an average of (3.95) and a standard deviation of (0.882). The second-place item was 39 (female managers involve teachers with information, data, and new systems) with an average of (3.93) and a standard deviation of (0.959). Item (45) (principals involve teachers in strategic planning of the school) ranked third with an average of (3.93) (just below the average of second rank) and a standard deviation of (0.910). The lowest response was item 43 (principals ensure that their actions match the values of the school) with an average of (3.88) and a standard deviation of (0.975).

Table No. 2shows the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the participants' responses to the dimensions of the learning organization. This table shows that the respondents' assessment of the degree of availability is high. The first dimension came in first with an average of (4.25) and a standard deviation of (0.430), which confirms the school's effort to find opportunities for continuous learning, followed by the second dimension, which is associated with encouraging interrogative and dialogue by the management with an average of (4.03) and standard deviation (0.624).In third place was the fourth dimension with an average of(4.01) and deviation (0.761) on the establishment of systems for knowledge sharing and learning, which are cooperative administrative dimensions and their logical arrangement as it indicates their compatibility.In fourth place was the third dimension encouraging cooperation and group learning with an average of (4.00) and deviation (0.754); in fifth place was the fifth dimension of enabling workers to gather them toward a common vision with an average of (4.00) justbelow the fourth rank and with a standard deviation of (0.795).In sixth place wasstrategic leadership with an average of (3.91) and a deviation of (0.849).In last place was thesixth dimension linked the organization to the external environment with an average of (3.88) and a standard deviation of (0.927).

Table (2) Averages and overall standard deviations for the questionnaire dimensions				
Arrange dimensions by average	standard deviation	Average	Statement	
1	0.430	4.25	The first dimension:Creating opportunities for continuous learning	A
2	0.624	4.03	The second dimension:Encouraging inquiry and dialogue	B
4	0.754	4.00	The third dimension:Encouraging cooperation and group learning	C
3	0.761	4.01	The fourth dimension:Creating systems for knowledge sharing and learning	D
5	0.795	4.00	The fifth dimension:Empowering employees to bring them together toward a common vision	E
7	0.927	3.88	The sixth dimension:Links the organization to the external environment	F
6	0.849	3.91	The seventh dimension:Strategic leadership	G
	0.683	4.01	Total	

The second study question: What is the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization with the school administration in secondary schools—girls inHawalli educational area—from the point of view of school administrations?

To answer this question, the answers of the principals and assistant principals in the two schools to the first and second question of the interview tool were analysed:

1. Do you think that the school administration is keen to implement the dimensions of the learning organization? And how?

Most of the sample members (6 participants) answered yes, that school administrations are keen to apply the dimensions of the learning organization.Four participants indicated that they are applied excellently, while two participants did not confirm the application of these dimensions. Onesaid, "I see that there are administrations trying to ensure the application of the dimensions of the organization." Anothersaid, "not all schools are aware of the need to have these seven dimensions and apply them in schools." Three of the participants stated that they implement the dimensions by holding workshops and courses or working through teams.One said, "Creating opportunities for continuous learning through the establishment of different and varied courses... As well as learning about global developments and trying to apply them,"andwe note that the participantfocused on two dimensions: continuing education and linking the organization to the external environment. A participant said, "There are deficiencies in some aspects in terms of the capabilities provided to management," which means it

may be difficult for management to apply the dimensions in an effective manner. Another said "they are applied in varying proportions," which means that there are indeed structured dimensions that are being applied, but not all are important for the school.

2. Through the exercise of your duties in the administration, what are the main foundations or principles on which you are based in your dealings with teachers, heads of departments or parents?

The participants' answers to the second question were aligned for four participants, indicating that commitment, trust, cooperation, constructive criticism, encouragement, and a positive spirit are principles followed by their school administrations. A participant said, "creating opportunities to acquire new experiences and train them in leadership and practice all administrative work" is the basic principle in working with teachers and department heads. One participant said that the principles on which the administration is based are "commitment to the application of rules and regulations and taking into account individual differences in performance and the difference in years of experience between teachers and the extent to which they are aware of the nature of work." We note that they talked about the main principles in their dealings and performance in school in general; they did not address any of the dimensions of the learning organization, perhaps indicating that they do not realize the importance of applying the dimensions. These answers contradict the responses of some participants to the first question.

The third study question: What are the most important obstacles to the application of the dimensions of the learning organization in secondary schools—girls in Hawalli educational area—from the point of view of school administrations?

Most agreed that finances are one of the most important obstacles that reduce the ability of administrations to apply the dimensions of the learning organization. One said, "the lack of sufficient money hinders the completion of most of the useful work, whether for the learner, teacher or school administration." Another said sudden decisions confuse the educational process. Three participants said that the job burden is an obstacle, and one said, "the large number of tasks required of school administrations, which consume effort and time and drain energy, which distracts administrations from paying attention to these dimensions." Another said "the most important obstacle is the lack of awareness of the concept of the learning organization and the inability to apply it in a proper way." Most participants stressed the need to provide financial support to schools to implement these dimensions and develop schools. A participant said, "financial support should be distributed by the ministry according to the density of the school." Another noted the importance of "finding supporters and sponsors who believe in the capabilities and achievements of public schools and aspire to raise the level of their performance." She also suggested using school canteens to generate profits for the school. Also, a participant recommended raising awareness of the importance of applying the dimensions of the learning organization and providing facilities. One said it is necessary to "spread awareness of the importance of applying the dimensions of the learning organization in schools in addition to providing facilities that help these departments in applying these dimensions," suggesting the administrations' awareness of these dimensions and the need to apply them in schools contributes significantly to enabling their application.

The fourth study question: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) in the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization in secondary schools—girls in Hawalli educational area—due to the variable of academic qualification, job experience and job title?

Table 9 (appendix 4) shows that there are no statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization in the sample schools due to the academic qualification, except for the first dimension. It was noted that there are significant differences on the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization in finding opportunities for continuous learning at a significant level (0.03) attributed to the academic qualification between the department head and teacher for those who have postgraduate degrees.

Table 10 (appendix 4) also shows that there are statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization in the sample schools in the first, fourth, fifth, sixth, and seventh dimensions (first dimension: creating opportunities for continuous learning at a significance level (0.02), fourth dimension: creating systems for sharing knowledge and learning at a significance level (0.01), fifth dimension: empowering employees to bring them together toward a common vision at a significance level (0.03), sixth dimension: connecting the organization with the external environment at a significance level (0.05), seventh dimension: leadership strategy is at a significance level (0.02), attributed for the job title between the head of the department and the teacher and in favour of the head of the department). There are also statistically significant differences in the degree of availability in the third dimension: encouraging cooperation and group learning at a significant level (0.02), attributable to the job title, between the head of the department and the teacher and for the benefit of the teacher. However, there were no statistically significant differences in the degree of

availability of the second dimension: encouraging interrogative and dialogue in the learning organization attributed to the job title, between the head of the department and the teacher.

Tables 11 and 12 (appendix 4) also show there are statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization—in the first, third, fourth, fifth, sixth and seventh dimensions (first dimension: finding opportunities for continuous learning at the level of morale (0.03), third dimension: encouraging cooperation and collective learning at the level of morale (0.02), fourth dimension: the establishment of systems for knowledge sharing and learning at the level of significance (0.001), fifth dimension: enabling employees to gather them toward a common vision at a moral level (0.001), sixth dimension: linking the organization to the external environment at a moral level (0.05), seventh dimension: strategic leadership at a moral level (0.03)) attributed to the variable of job experience between the department head and teacher, in favour of more than 10 years' experience, and with a between-sample variation at a (0.01) significance level.

Discussion of the results:

First question

The quantitative results showed that teachers and heads of departments' assessment of the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization in secondary schools in the Hawalli area was high. However, its application in schools was not of the same degree or did not take the same degree of importance as school administrations. The first dimension came in first place because it is rooted in creating opportunities for continuous learning, followed by the second dimension, which encourages interrogative and dialogue by the management of the learning organization. In third place was the fourth dimension, which is related to the establishment of systems for sharing knowledge and learning, which are cooperative administrative dimensions and demonstrate their compatibility to achieve continuous development in the school. In fourth place was encouraging cooperation and collective learning, perhaps because schools have become training centres that provide courses and workshops for their teachers, which contributes to the existence of the learning organization. This aligns with Al-Wahid and Al-Faftoh (2020) in that the learning organization has administrative and organizational requirements as well as human requirements to contribute to the application of its provisions.

The three dimensions that came in the last ranks are: after enabling employees to gather them toward a common vision in fifth place, due to the management's belief that the vision must start from the administration and be presented to the board of directors, which weakens the role of the teachers. In sixth place was strategic leadership, perhaps because the teachers did not know what leadership is and think they do not have the right to participate. In seventh and last place was linking the organization to the external environment because there are systems and regulations from the senior administrations in the educational region or the Ministry of Education that regulate the school's relationship with the external environment. Systems encourage community participation with schools, but restrict them, which reduced the desire of teachers or departments to deal with the external environment. This contradicts the study Zubr (2019) in which leadership was an essential feature of the learning organization that supports an inclusive learning culture.

However, despite the varying responses on each dimension of the learning organization, the results indicate their availability in the study sample; that is, these dimensions are available to a high to medium degree, which leads to an interactive developmental role for the administrative and educational process and achieves a qualitative development in the efficiency of the school and its performance. This aligns with Al-Hammadi (2021), Al-Shaya and Al-Sheikh (2022), Al-Harbi (2018), Al-Anzi (2017), Al-Ghamdi (2016), Al-Ayasrah and Al-Harhi (2013), Sai-rat et al. (2015), which all indicated a high degree of school management practice for the learning organization.

However, it differs from Khanfar (2021), Beljahr (2021), Al-Azmi (2021), Awwad and Al-Harbi (2015), and Can (2011), in which the application of the dimensions of the learning organization obtained average response scores. The study of Ghahramanifard et al. (2013) indicated that sample schools had low degrees of ability to apply the dimensions of the learning organization.

The data of the first dimension also indicated that the two schools have created opportunities for continuous learning for their affiliates, which achieves one of the dimensions of the learning organization. The item "I cooperate with teachers to carry out learning processes" followed by the item "I discuss with teachers about functional errors in order to learn and benefit" received high responses, which confirms that there are opportunities for continuous learning because there is cooperation between teachers and discussions that clarify functional errors to be overcome. This result is natural because teachers may feel the need for clarification of educational activities and work, which will result in exchanging experiences. Yet, the item of rewards that teachers receive from the administration when learning new knowledge or skills received the lowest response rate, and this may be due to the administration's lack of awareness of its role because it believes it is the responsibility of the teacher to develop herself through continuous learning or perhaps because of the weak financial support or restrictions imposed on schools by the ministry. Despite this, the response is relatively high,

which confirms that the two schools are organizations that apply the first dimension of the learning organization, which aligns with the study of Abu Deeb (2022), but contradicts the study of Al-Hammadi (2021), in which this dimension ranked last.

The data of the second dimension indicated the spread of the culture of dialogue among the sample groups, which reflects the availability of encouraging interrogative and dialogue and enhances the high availability of this dimension with school administrations. The participants ranked "The administration encourages me to ask different questions with their acceptance" and the item "I exchange with the teacher's feedback among us transparently" highest in this axis, which is consistent with the responses in the first axis, where the participants indicated that there are discussions to exchange information between them, which helps in building good relations. "The administration listens to the views of others and is respected and appreciated" earned the lowest response rate, perhaps because the teachers' communication with the administration is through the department heads, which reduced the response rate to this item. However, this did not affect the high rate of responses to this dimension, as it ranked second in this study, which is inconsistent with Al-Hammadi (2021), in which this dimension ranked fifth.

As for the third dimension of the learning organization, the results indicated that there is a clear and significant encouragement for cooperation and collective learning and is actually practiced, which reflects the availability of the dimensions of the learning organization in these departments. The first item, "The school administration is keen on the work based on the formation of teams in all fields," and the third item, "The school administration deals with the members of the work teams equally regardless of any differences between them," had the highest response rates in this dimension, perhaps because of the belief of school administrations in the importance of work teams in achieving the goals of the school. Yet, the item "The school administration grants sufficient powers to the work teams to achieve the school's goals" received the lowest response rate, perhaps because the school administration believes that teams need guidance and follow-up, or because the administration is concerned about losing control. After encouraging collaboration and group learning, it ranked fourth, consistent with Al Hammadi's study (2021). But it contradicts Al-Azmi's study (2021), which indicated that the response to this dimension was medium. However, this is not at all consistent with the study of Ghahramanifardetal. (2013), which indicated that this dimension is not available in schools.

As for the fourth dimension, the data indicates the existence of a system for data management and performance measurement in the learning organization to share knowledge and effective communication within it. In this dimension, both "The school administration has measurement systems to know the results of training and development processes in the school and its impact on teachers" and "The school administration allows everyone to benefit from its previous experiences" had the highest response rate in this axis, which means that the organization encourages the sharing of knowledge through training and development systems that are prepared and delivered in the school. This is probably due to the keenness of senior management (represented by the Hawalli Educational Zone) to activate performance improvement teams (as known from the researcher's work experience in Hawalli schools), which is responsible for following up on teachers' participation in training courses, in addition to exchanging visits between teachers and attending professional development, activities, and other methods of development and development that teachers share. However, in the same dimension, the lowest response rate were "The school administration keeps up-to-date data on the skills possessed by teachers" and "The school administration provides an up-to-date database on the school and students to be used in the schoolwork of teachers," perhaps because the preservation of this data is an administrative matter that some teachers may not know about. This does not diminish the availability of this fourth dimension in the two schools, which increases their value as learning organizations. This dimension ranked third in this study, which is inconsistent with Al-Hammadi (2021).

As for the fifth dimension, which is the empowerment of workers to bring them together toward a common vision, its highest response was "The school administration invites teachers to contribute and participate in enriching its strategic vision" and then the item "The school administration allows freedom of choice for teachers when carrying out tasks." This is perhaps due to the awareness of school administrations that the school's vision must be shared by everyone to succeed, as well as its belief that the involvement of teachers and heads of departments must be according to their choice so that they can achieve and achieve the goals. This indicates the awareness of the administrations of the importance of forming a common vision. However, the item "The school administration supports everyone when carrying out their tasks, no matter how dangerous" received a medium or low response rate compared to the rest of the items of this dimension, perhaps due to the administration's hesitation or perhaps because of the existence of systems and laws that limit the administration's ability to act freely. Overall, this dimension ranked fifth, consistent with Al-Azmi's study (2021) according to the classification of the Singh model (Senge, 1990). However, this is not consistent with Ghahramanifardetal.(2013) and others, which indicated that this dimension is not available in the schools of their study samples, and, in the study of Al-Hammadi (2021), it ranked first and in Al-Harbi (2018) it ranked second.

The responses of the participants on the sixth dimension indicated the existence of a system that establishes the learning environment and cooperation with the external environment for development, development and achievement of its goals, and thus affects and is affected by the local and internal community, but to an average degree compared to the rest of the dimensions. "School administration encourages everyone to think from a global perspective" was the highest response in this dimension, perhaps due to the frequent use of social media and access to the experiences of others, which made administrations encourage more exposure to other cultures after they felt a positive impact on the school environment. "The school administration encourages everyone to take into account the views of the beneficiaries (students and their parents) when making important decisions" also ranked second, due to the presence of parents' councils and their participation and perhaps because of their material and moral contributions. Certainly, they have an influential role in school decisions. The item "the school administration is interested in knowing the impact of its decisions on the conditions of teachers," received the lowest response rate in this dimension, perhaps due to the large preoccupation of school administrations with the application of systems and regulations, and their preoccupation with following up on educational developments, especially given the explosion of knowledge and technology and the race to achieve excellence at the level of schools in the region. The follow-up by Hawalli Educational District to evaluate distinguished schools may lead school administrations to not pay attention to the conditions of teachers or the impact of their decisions on them. We note that this dimension ranked seventh and last among the dimensions of the learning organization, which contradicts the study of Al-Hammadi (2021), in which it ranked second.

For the results of the seventh and final dimension, it was noted that "Transfer of administrative expertise to teachers to empower them administratively and leadership" received the highest response rate, which confirms the keenness of departments to transfer experiences. This indicates the awareness of departments of the importance of forming teams and working through them. The items "Principals involve teachers with new information, data and systems" and "Principals involve teachers in the strategic planning of the school" also ranked second and third, respectively, with very close scores in the arithmetic average (3.93), as these two items complement each other. This may be due to the awareness of the principals that strategic planning will not succeed without full participation, and their awareness that their involvement and familiarity with the new data, information and systems will certainly help their participation in developing plans. The strategy is effective based on strong foundations, to inform them of data and their knowledge of systems, which emphasizes the role of the director in transferring experiences to teachers and empowering them administratively. The least responsive item was "Principals are keen to match their actions with the values of the school," perhaps because the principals adhere to the application of rules and regulations and believe that their values and habits should be separated from the school community. These results indicate the existence of organized efforts and educational construction strategies in the sample schools, which confirm the application of the dimensions of the learning organization, but with an average degree of availability on the strategic leadership dimension compared to the rest of the dimensions, which is inconsistent with the study of Al-Hammadi (2021).

Second and third questions

From the analysis of qualitative data obtained from interviews conducted with school administrations (two principals and four assistant directors) we noted there is an application of some dimensions of the organization, but also, not at the required level. This is evident when asked how; the answers were generally hesitant about learning and sharing experiences. Perhaps this applies to the responses of teachers and heads of departments who confirmed the existence of the application of the dimensions of the organization to a high degree of the first five dimensions and to a medium degree to the last two dimensions, which are related to management tasks. Although the participants (in interviews) tried to give the impression that the dimensions were applied in an excellent way, the results indicate that there is a degree of variability of some dimensions. This was confirmed by a participant, where she said "not all schools are aware of the need for these seven dimensions," and another respondent who noted that "there are departments that try to ensure the application of the dimensions of the organization," which means that there is not enough awareness by the administrations of the importance of all dimensions. This is not in accordance with researchers and experts in the field of educational administration, as they stressed that the learning organization is a continuous process that stems from the vision of organization members. Al-Maghribi and Marzouk (2016, 14 on the frenzy of 1998) as well as Al-Ruwaili (2022, p. 131) asserted that the learning organization is an "integrated system" with different leadership positions and job experiences for the members of the organization, and Singh's model for the learning organization indicates the importance of training cadres and awareness of the concept of the learning organization (Coldwell & Fried, 2012)

Also, most of the answers to the question of "how" focused only on holding workshops and courses and working with teams, as if the dimensions of the organization were limited only to the first dimension, which is "creating opportunities for continuous learning," not to mention shortcomings in mentioned in other aspects. Also, one participant said that the application was in varying proportions, which suggests it was not applied properly, or there was lack of knowledge about the seven dimensions of the learning organization. This was confirmed by the

participants' responses to the second interview question, as they talked about the main principles in their dealings and performance in school in general; this indicates that they do not realize the importance of applying all dimensions of the learning organization, and these answers contradict what was stated by some participants to the first interview question, where the answer was "Yes, applied excellently."

The answers to the question of obstacles confirmed that there is a deficiency in the application of some dimensions of the learning organization in secondary schools in the Hawalli educational area. More than one participant indicated that the lack of material resources leads to the inability of schools to apply the dimensions of the learning organization to achieve their goals, and this is consistent with Al-Wahid and Al-Fantouh (2020), who indicated that there are requirements for the learning organization, including material and technical requirements. One of the most important obstacles mentioned by the interviewees is ".... Lack of awareness of the concept of the learning organization and the inability to apply it properly," which means the inability to apply the seven dimensions of the learning organization at the required level.

Therefore, it was necessary to propose appropriate solutions from the point of view of school administrations, which are better able to assess their needs and develop solutions to the obstacles they face. One of these solutions is to provide financial support by finding easy and flexible mechanisms for disbursement from the school canteen and the financial fund, and not to restrict school administrations when using school resources for the benefit of schools, or to encourage civil society institutions and parents to donate to or sponsor schools, as this helps in applying the dimensions of the organization and raising the level and development of schools. A participant also said there is a need to raise awareness among school administrations of the importance of applying the dimensions of the learning organization in schools and providing facilities to these schools so that they realize their importance. In addition, reducing administrative burdens and increasing legal and regulatory flexibility would allow for real participation of female workers in the field.

Fourth question

There were statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization attributed to the scientific qualification in favour of those with postgraduate studies, which is to find opportunities for continuous learning. This was an expected result as those who completed their graduate studies believe in the importance of continuous learning, and have ability to participate in achieving continuous learning for her colleagues through the transfer of knowledge, whether in the cognitive and scientific aspect or practical and field side. However, this contradicts Awwad and Al-Harbi (2015), which indicated that there are differences due to academic qualification in favour of the bachelor's and diploma categories, and the studies of Al-Ghamdi (2016), Al-Ayasrah and Al-Harthy (2013), which indicated that there were no statistically significant differences according to this variable.

The data also indicated that there are statistically significant differences in the first, fourth, fifth, sixth and seventh dimensions attributed to the job title between the head of the department and the teacher in favour of the head of the department because these dimensions are closer to the role of the head of the department, which is associated with the tasks of management such as strategic leadership, sharing the vision, linking the school to the external environment and establishing learning systems. This is consistent with the Beljahr study (2021) which showed significant differences due to the nature of the work for the benefit of those who are higher in the job level. However, it contradicts Al-Shaya and Al-Sheikh (2022), which found that no differences due to the variable of the nature of work except in "strategic leadership" but in favour of female teachers.

There are also statistically significant differences in the third dimension: "encouraging cooperation and collective learning" due to job title, but in favour of teachers, because the teacher bears the responsibility of developing her skills and participating in the learning processes to exchange experiences. This is also indicated by the data of Table 5, which shows the degree of availability of the third dimension of the learning organization through the administration's keenness to form work teams, where the teacher finds opportunity for collective learning with her colleagues. This is consistent with Tan and Olaore (2021) that confirmed that the dimensions of a learning organization affect the effectiveness and efficiency of all employees at any job level.

There are also statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of the dimensions of the learning organization—in the first, third, fourth, fifth, sixth and seventh dimensions due to job experience in favour of experience of more than 10 years. This is a logical and acceptable consequence of expertise in increasing the awareness of teachers and heads of departments of the importance of applying the dimensions of the learning organization. This supports Al-Ayasrah and Al-Harthy (2013), but contradicts the study of Al-Zahrani and Al-Sharif (2017), which showed that there are statistically significant differences due to the number of years of experience in favour of those with five to less than 10 years of experience, and the studies of Al-Ghamdi (2016), Al-Shaya and Al-Sheikh (2022), Khanfar (2021) and Beljahr (2021), which indicated that there are no statistically significant differences due to years of experience.

Recommendations:

- The necessity of teaching this concept and its basic dimensions in teacher preparation colleges as an input in educational administration.
- Spread awareness in educational communities about the concept of the learning organization and the importance of achieving it through the application of its basic dimensions.
- Prepare specialized training programs on the application of the learning organization in educational institutions.
- Propose the administrative concept (learning organization) as one of the criteria for distinguished schools in performance, which are selected at the end of each academic year.
- Provide material and moral support to schools that seek to implement the learning organization.
- Grant educational institutions more administrative powers to enable them to adopt and benefit from modern administrative strategies and concepts.
- Work to guide senior leaders in educational institutions to involve workers in planning, design, implementation, supervision, and follow-up, as well as evaluation and evaluation.
- Activate work teams and distributing tasks in a balanced and fair manner among the institution's affiliates.
- Conduct more research and studies on the extent to which the learning organization is applied, its importance, its effects on the institution and its most important obstacles.

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